

Concepts as Carrier of Cultural Memory: The Soul from *Beowulf* to the *King James Bible**

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Abstract: This study traces the main shadows of meaning the word soul, as an intrinsically religious concept, acquired throughout its history from the Middle Ages to early modernity. The article examines the usage of the word through six texts spanning Old English to Early Modern English: *Beowulf* (c. eighth–eleventh century), *The Vespasian Psalter* (c. eighth century), *The Paston Letters* (1465), Edmund Spenser's *The Faerie Queene* (1596), John Donne's *Holy Sonnets* (c. 1609–1617), and *King James Bible* (1611).

Theoretically, the study draws on cultural memory as conceptualised by Jan Assmann (2008). Methodologically, the research draws on conceptual history, connecting literary usage to broader religious and political history, integrating approaches from historical linguistics (orthographic and semantic change), cultural history and discourse analysis (usage in specific contexts).

The results demonstrate that 'soul' started its semantic journey in Old English as a pagan Germanic word that was – together with other entities – an intrinsic part of a fourfold model for human psychology. It then acquired more comprehensive semantic layers after the Christianisation of Britain and was integrated – under the influence of theological translations from Latin – within a Scholastic bipartite model that combined the different human psychological and intellectual functions in a unitary soul.

It was not long before the soul began to integrate a holistic sense, referring to the whole person during the 1300s. As Christianity became more institutionally and socially established in the Late Middle Ages, 'soul' took on another shade of meaning that made it more closely tied to domestic care and one's personal welfare. However, as the Reformation shook many of the older religious and social tenets, 'soul' acquired yet a new layer of meaning as a psychological entity that was both a subject to and an active agent in the social, theological and personal turmoil of the time. During this semantic trajectory, different institutions maintained the preservation and transmission of the word's cultural memory. The article identifies the ones that were prominent in each period.

Keywords: Soul, cultural memory, conceptual history, Old English, Middle English, paganism, Christianisation.

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Kültürel Hâfızanın Taşıyıcısı Olarak Kavramlar: İngilizce *Soul* Sözcüğü *Beowulf*tan *King James Bible*'a

Öz: Bu çalışma, zamanla ağırlıklı olarak dinsel bir anlam kazanan *soul* sözcüğünün, Orta Çağ'dan erken modern döneme uzanan tarihi boyunca edindiği başlıca anlam gölgelerini izlemektedir. Makale, sözcüğün kullanımını Eski İngilizce'den Erken Modern İngilizce'ye uzanan altı metin üzerinden incelemektedir: *Beowulf* (y. 8.-11. yüzyıl), *The Vespasian Psalter* (y. 8. yüzyıl), *The Paston Letters* (1465), Edmund Spenser'in *The Faerie Queene*'i (1596), John Donne'un *Holy Sonnets*'i (1609-1617) ve *King James Bible* (1611).

Teorik açıdan çalışma, Jan Assmann'ın (2008) kültürel hâfıza kuramı çerçevesinde şekillenmektedir. Yöntem açısından ise araştırma kavram tarihinden yararlanmakta; edebî kullanımı daha geniş dinsel ve siyasal tarihle ilişkilendirmekte; tarihsel dilbilim (yazım ve anlam değişiklikleri), kültürel tarih ve söylem çözümlemesi (belirli bağlamlardaki kullanım) yaklaşımlarını bir araya getirmektedir.

Bulgular, *soul* sözcüğünün anlamsal yolculuğuna Eski İngilizce'de pagan Cermen kökenli bir sözcük olarak başladığını ve – *mod*, *hyge*, *feorh* gibi diğer kavramlarla birlikte – insan psikolojisine dair dörtlü bir modelin ayrılmaz bir parçası olduğunu göstermektedir. Sözcük, Britanya'nın Hristiyanlaşmasının ardından daha kapsamlı anlam genişlemelerine uğramış; Latince'den yapılan teolojik çevirilerin etkisiyle, insanın farklı psikolojik ve entelektüel işlevlerini tek bir *soul*'da birleştiren Skolastik ikili model içine eklenmiştir.

Çok geçmeden *soul*, 1300'lü yıllarda kapsayıcı bir anlam kazanmaya ve tüm insana atıfta bulunmaya başlamıştır. Geç Orta Çağ'da Hristiyanlık kurumsal ve toplumsal olarak daha da yerleşik hale geldikçe, *soul* yeni bir anlam tonu daha kazanmış; bireysel esenlikle daha yakından ilişkilendirilmiştir. Ancak Reformasyon eski dinsel ve toplumsal ilkelerin pek çoğunu sarsarken, *soul* bir kez daha yeni bir anlam gölgesi edinmiş; dönemin toplumsal, teolojik ve kişisel çalkantılarının hem nesnesi hem de etkin bir faili olan psikolojik bir varlık haline gelmiştir.

Bu anlamsal yolculuk boyunca, farklı kurumlar sözcüğün kültürel hâfızasının aktarımını üstlenmiştir. Makale, her dönemde öne çıkan bu kurumları tespit etmektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: *Soul*, Kültürel hâfıza, Kavram tarihi, Eski İngilizce, Orta İngilizce, Paganizm, Hristiyanlaşma.

Introduction

There is indeed community between past and present, but also that *community* – that difficult word – is not the only possible description of these relations between past and present; [...] there are also radical change, discontinuity and conflict, and [...] all these are still at issue and are indeed still occurring (Williams, 1985, p. 83).

Across cultural memory studies, the past is a culturally mediated resource. Through shared symbols, narratives and practices, it frames what feels meaningful, thinkable and possible in the present, while remaining open to contestation and reinterpretation. This study combines Jan Assmann's theory of cultural memory (*kulturelles Gedächtnis*) with Reinhart Koselleck's conceptual history (*Begriffsgeschichte*) to explore some of the cultural memories the word *soul* acquired during about 900 years of its history.

From Koselleck (2011), the study adopts the distinction between a word and a basic concept (*Grundbegriff*). A word becomes a concept when it absorbs numerous semantic elements. Koselleck illustrates this distinction using the example of the word 'state'. He explains that various elements – such as 'domination, territorial sovereignty, administration, citizenship, legislation, adjudication, taxation, and military force' – come together in the word 'state', with their complex subject matter and vocabulary, to transform it into a concept. While we can distinguish between a word's literal meaning (*Bedeutung*) and what it refers to (*das Bedeutetes*), a concept fuses these together. Historical reality enters the word's ambiguity so thoroughly that the reality can only be understood through that word itself.

The study also adopts Koselleck's (2011) central premise of revealing 'the contemporaneity of the noncontemporaneous (*Gleichzeitigkeit des Ungleichzeitigen*)' within a concept. A concept often carries the sediment of multiple historical eras simultaneously. Conceptual history operates as a bridge between the vanished social contexts of the past and our present understanding. Cultural memory complements this framework by supplying the institutional remembering/forgetting mechanism that keeps the past alive/buried. Together, they allow the analysis to identify how a *Grundbegriff* like 'soul' carries multiple, sometimes contradictory *Zeitschichten* (time layers), and how past meanings continue to influence spiritual, psychological and social imagination through the very words available to speak about it.

As conceptualised by Jan Assmann (2008), cultural memory – unlike personal memory, which is bounded by a lifetime, or collective memory, which does not exceed the life span of three generations – extends across centuries. Collective memory only becomes cultural memory when it is anchored in institutional frameworks, such as religious rites, educational curricula, museums, archives, monuments or other media. These institutions codify and ritualise selected narratives, providing memory sites where the past can be stored, rehearsed and transmitted to successive audiences.

Because cultural memory operates on a temporal scale far larger than lived experience, its maintenance requires specialists (historians, theologians, archivists, curators, educators, etc.) who possess the knowledge and methodological tools to interpret, curate and transmit the preserved memories. These experts mediate between the raw historical record and the public, determining what is remembered and what is 'forgotten', shaping the meanings that become part of a community's shared identity. This makes cultural memory selective, institutionally supported and hence intrinsically tied to power dynamics.

Cultural memory is carried by symbols (e.g. texts, images, monuments, digital media). Concepts are such symbols. The concept of the soul is par excellence a cultural symbol, a *Grundbegriff* (to use Koselleck's word) and a cultural 'keyword', to use Raymond Williams' ([1976] 1985) label. It carries within its four letters a map of social, political, religious and intellectual changes in the 'English' culture. Like other 'keywords', the meaning of 'soul' is often contested and relational. Its meaning is a history of competing uses tied to power and perspective, operating within semantic networks of other words.

The concept of the soul has been extensively studied from a theological perspective (Swinburne, 1997; Baker and Goetz, 2011), philosophically (Loose et al., 2018; Crisp et al., 2016), and historically, tracing changing religious practices involving souls (Bynum, 1995; Marshall, 2002). Cultural historians have also explored changing concepts of selfhood and identity (Taylor, 1989; Martin, 2004), while historical linguists have documented the phonological and orthographic development of *sāwol* > *soule* > soul as part of broader studies of English sound changes and spelling standardisation. Nevertheless, most of the studies focus on the past as history. This article studies the past as memory, that is, the past as remembered (and forgotten) in the present. The focus is the shadows the history of 'soul' casts on its present, showing how competing memories coexist within

a single word. The central research questions are: what memory layers did the word soul accumulate since its beginning till the seventeenth century, particularly in the religious and literary contexts? What memory-hosts appear to have shaped those layers in six representative textual moments spanning the period?

To identify distinct memory layers in the word 'soul', the analysis applies two complementary criteria. On the one hand, the form of 'soul' is chronologically traced from the Old-English *sāwol/sāwel*, to the Middle-English variations (*soule*, *sowle*, *saule*, *sawle*) to the Early-Modern standardisation (*soule*), and each is linked to deeper semantic changes. On the other, the word is studied within specific textual contexts. Each passage is situated within the historical and cultural context that produced it, noting how institutions condition the way the concept is used and understood.

The article traces the word 'soul' through six texts spanning Old English to Early Modern English: *Beowulf* (c. eighth–eleventh century), *The Vespasian Psalter* (c. eighth century), *The Paston Letters* (1465), Edmund Spenser's *The Faerie Queene* (1596), John Donne's *Holy Sonnets* (c. 1609–1617), and *King James Bible* (1611). While these works are by no means comprehensive, they are culturally influential texts that provide chronological coverage across about 900 years, and ensure genre diversity (epic poetry, liturgy, private letters, allegorical epic, devotional poetry, biblical translation) and key moments of semantic change (Christianisation, pastoral intensification, rise of lay piety, Protestant redefinition).

This study does not claim statistical representativeness. The six texts are used to identify some of the layers of meanings the word 'soul' acquired. Findings about memory transmission are suggestive rather than exhaustive. The study is further limited to literary and religious texts, excluding legal, medical and philosophical genres where 'soul' may carry additional meanings. Also, the study stops at 1611; the subsequent semantic history of 'soul' – including its Romantic psychologisation, its secularisation in the Victorian period, and its re-emergence in late twentieth-century therapeutic and popular culture contexts – remains beyond the scope of this article.

By examining how 'soul' functions linguistically and conceptually in each context, this study demonstrates that the word's present-day semantic range – from a metaphysical entity to psychological interiority to romantic connection (e.g. soulmate) – inherits centuries of semantic layering where theological debates, translation choices, literary innovations and cultural crises have deposited competing meanings that coexist, often uncomfortably, in modern English.

1. Earliest Beginnings

After the Roman legions withdrew from Britain around 410 CE, a power vacuum ensued. Into this void came the Germanic settlers. By the mid-fifth century CE, the Germanic dialects spoken by the Angles, Saxons and Jutes had taken root in Britain, giving rise to what we now call Old English. Old-English literature is preserved mostly in West Saxon and blends pagan and Christian traditions (Baugh & Cable, 2005). The cultural-religious context for the Old English 'soul' thus begins with

England's Christianisation during the sixth–eighth centuries (Mayr-Harting, 1972; Blair, 2005). The conversion required translating Latin texts and Christian concepts into Germanic cultural frameworks. As Peter Brown demonstrated in *The Rise of Western Christendom* (2003), Christianisation was a complex negotiation with paganism, producing hybrid Christianities adapted to local cultures.

By around 700 CE, Christianity had been nominally established throughout England. Nonetheless,

[d]espite the enormous influence of the Church, earlier pagan practices remained, [...] for example, in the names of the weekdays, Tuesday (*tīwesdæg*), Wednesday (*wōdnesdæg*), Thursday (*þunresdæg*), and Friday (*frīgedæg*), all named for Nordic gods: Tiu, the god of war and the sky; Woden; Thor, the god of thunder (*þunor*); and Frīg, goddess of domestic love and the hearth. Likewise, Easter took its name from Eastre, the dawn-goddess (Gramley & Gramley, 2005, p. 37).

The Viking invasions, beginning in the late eighth century, triggered another crucial development. As Norse raiders settled and threatened the Anglo-Saxon identity, King Alfred the Great (r. 871–899) launched a remarkable program of translation into and writing in English in the late ninth century to help establish a common religious-intellectual ground among the common people. This effort made religious works accessible to the English-speaking populace and contributed to the standardisation of written Old English, which employed the Latin alphabet and several runic¹ letters that have since fallen out of use, such as the thorn (þ), edth (ð), aesch (æ) and yogh (ȝ).

The oldest and most persistent words in Old English consisted largely of single-syllable words naming the fundamentals of existence, like *sunne* (sun), *mōna* (moon), *mann* (man), *wīf* (woman), *heafod* (head) and *ƿot* (foot) (Lerer, 2007, pp. 7–8). These monosyllabic words carried immense semantic weight and were flexible enough to survive the great upheavals of invasion, conquest and standardisation. ‘Soul’ belongs firmly in this group. Like God, love, life and death, it encapsulates a fundamental human concern, and its longevity in the language reflects its enduring cultural importance.

Soul traces its lineage to Old-English *sāwol* (also *sāw(e)l*, *saul*, *saule*, *saula*, *saulae*), an inheritance from the Proto-Germanic **saiwalō*.² Unlike many abstract or spiritual terms introduced into English via Latin³ (spirit), Greek (psyche) or French (person, ultimately from Latin), ‘soul’ is a native Germanic word. Its presence in the earliest English texts places it within the oldest semantic strata of the language as a relic of England’s earliest spiritual lexicon.

¹ The runes are a Germanic-designed alphabet created in the early centuries CE. The Old English word *rūn* itself originally meant ‘secret, mystery, dark mysterious statement, (secret) council’ (Harper, n.d.). While the common view in runology postulates that the runes largely derived from Latin letters, some scholars argue that at least some of the runic characters come from the Nabatean variety of the Aramaic Semitic alphabet (Troeng, 2003). Others contend that ‘runic writing derives directly from the Phoenician writing system of the Carthaginians who dominated the Atlantic coasts from the fifth to the end of the third century’ (Nierfeld, 2006). A third theory suggests the runic script has Turkic origins (Çayır, 2024).

² The asterisk (*) denotes a reconstructed proto-form.

³ In his etymological dictionary of the German language, Friedrich Kluge (1891) notes that there might be an etymological relation between Latin *saeculum*, ‘age, generation’ (literally ‘vital power’), and *saiwalō*.

Though its ultimate origin remains uncertain and contested, some etymologists, drawing on Germanic philology, suggest that the Proto-Germanic form **saiwalō* might be a derivative of **saiwaz*, the word for ‘lake’ or ‘sea’, implying an original meaning akin to ‘that which belongs to or comes from the lake’, possibly reflecting early ancient Germanic animistic or pagan beliefs about the soul’s origin or destination (that souls resided in or came from bodies of water, both before birth and after death). Alternatively, some scholars suggest that it might be related to another pre-Christian Germanic belief where the soul was linked to breath and air as a life force. While the universality of these beliefs is debated, such a derivation reflects the early mytho-poetic connection between the soul and natural elements (Pfeifer, 1993).

With the Christianisation of England (597 CE onward), ‘soul’ became central to the English theological vocabulary. It generally denoted ‘the intellectual and immortal principle in man [... or] a human creature (after death), living being’. Many OE words were based on these meanings, e.g. *sáwolberend* (being with a soul, human being), *sáwolhús* (soul-house, body), *sáwolgedál* (the parting of soul and body, death), *sáwolhord* (treasure of the soul, life guarded as a treasure in the body, the body full of life), and *sáwolléas* (soulless, without soul; lifeless, without life) (Johnson, 1927/2004). Old English literature typically depicts the soul entering the body in various scenarios, mainly in original creation (Adam and Eve), prenatal ensoulment (ordinary conception/birth), the revival of a dead person (miraculous resuscitations) and eschatological resurrection (the end times). In each case, animation, that is the transition from lifeless matter to a living being, occurs through the soul’s entrance into the body, reinforcing the central premise that life and the presence of the soul are inseparable (Lockett, 2011, p. 19). With Christianisation, the word ‘soul’ came to encode doctrines of salvation, judgment and resurrection. In this context, the ‘soul’ was both a metaphysical essence and a moral subject that is affected by sin, grace and divine justice.

2. Old English *Sāwol*: Excerpt from *Beowulf* (700–1000 CE)⁴

Beowulf bridges the pre-Christian Germanic oral tradition and the Christian literate culture. The poem was likely composed orally (possibly in the eighth century) but was later preserved in monastic manuscript (Cotton Vitellius A.xv, c. 1000), showing 200–300 years of cultural layering. Its heroic-Christian synthesis reveals pre-Christian substrate meanings (‘soul’ as vital force, honour-bound warrior essence) and demonstrates that Christian *sāwol* was imposed onto a Germanic word with a different semantic range, creating semantic stratification, where earlier layers show through later ones.

While *sāwol* appears sparingly in *Beowulf*, which is more preoccupied with heroic *wyrd* (fate) than Christian eschatology, its usage offers a glimpse into the term’s pre-modern semantic breadth.

⁴ *Beowulf* is generally regarded as the earliest surviving Old English epic poem written around 700 CE. It tells the story of a Scandinavian hero named Beowulf who fights monsters. No medieval source names an author, and the surviving manuscript (c. 1000) gives no attribution (Neidorf, 2017). The common view is that a single, highly educated Christian Anglo-Saxon poet authored the epic now preserved, though many scribal errors crept into the poem throughout the centuries. Some scholars, however, argue that the methods used to claim unity of authorship are flawed and that different sections in the poem may reflect different authors or substantial revision, contending that the poem was originally pagan, and the Christian passages were incorporated later (Hulbert, 1951).

The Old English excerpt below is taken from the *Electronic Beowulf* (Kiernan, 2023), and the Modern English verse follows R. M. Liuzza's translation (2000).

Hwilum hie geheton æt hrærgtrafum
At times they offered honor to idols

wigweorþunga, wordum bædon
at pagan temples, prayed aloud

þæt him gastþona geoce gefremede
that the **soul-slayer** might offer assistance

wið þeodþream. Swylc wæs þeaw hyra,
in the country's distress. Such was their custom,

hæþenra hyht. Helle gemundon
the hope of heathens — they remembered hell

in modsefan, Metod hie ne cuþon,
in their minds, they did not know the Maker,

dæda Demend, ne wiston hie Drihten God.
the Judge of deeds, they did not know the Lord God,

Ne hie huru heofena Helm herian ne cuþon,
or even how to praise the heavenly Protector,

wuldres Waldend. Wa bið þæm ðe sceal
Wielder of glory. Woe unto him

þurh sliðne nið sawle bescufan
who must thrust his **soul** through wicked force

in fyres fæþm, frofre ne wenan,
in the fire's embrace, expect no comfort,

...

These verses (lines 175–188) occur early in the poem. In the story, a terrible monster named Grendel has been ravaging Heorot, the great hall of the Danish king Hrothgar. For twelve years, this creature has been killing Danish warriors, and no one could stop him. Unable to defeat the monster, the Danes turned to pagan worship at *hrærgtrafum* (shrines/temples of idols), seeking help through heathen rites. However, young Beowulf, a warrior from Geatland (southern Sweden), sails to help Hrothgar. He kills Grendel, then descends into a watery mere to kill Grendel's avenging mother with a giant sword ...

Rather than depicting an abandonment of Christian faith by Christian characters, the passage reflects the poet's Christian retrospective judgment on a pre-Christian people. The narrator pauses the story to comment on the spiritual danger of the Danes' actions, saying that because they did not know the true Christian God, they were turning in the wrong direction. Scholars like Dorothy Whitelock (*The Audience of Beowulf*, 1951) and J.R.R. Tolkien (*Beowulf: The Monsters and the Critics*, [1936] 1983) emphasise the poem's dual cultural heritage with its pagan setting filtered through a Christian lens.

The Old English word *sāwol* appears as *sawle* in the accusative case. The verse presents the soul as something that can be ‘thrust’ (*bescufan*) into damnation through evil actions. This active verb suggests choice and responsibility; souls are actively endangered through human decisions. In this context, the passage juxtaposes immediate needs (*þeodþreaum*, ‘the people’s distress’) with eternal consequences (souls thrust into fire), which reflects the Christian worldview where temporal suffering is preferable to eternal damnation.

However, earlier in the same passage, the ModE version mentions the word ‘soul’ (in **soul-slayer**) as a translation of the compound *gastbona*, which refers to the ‘Devil [as in] the Middle Ages the gods of the pagans were often regarded as demons in disguise’ (Liuzza, 2000, p. 59). The modern translation ‘soul-slayer’ captures the general meaning for contemporary readers who understand this refers to something that destroys a person’s spiritual essence. However, the original Old English was more nuanced.

Gast is the OE spelling for ‘ghost’. It carries otherworldly, supernatural connotations and is used to convey various meanings, namely ‘breath; good or bad spirit, angel, demon; person, man, human being’. In Old-English Christian texts, *gast* was used to translate the Latin word *spiritus*, a meaning that endures in the phrase ‘Holy Ghost’. The sense we most commonly use today of ‘ghost’ as ‘the disembodied spirit of a dead person’, especially one thought to be visible or to haunt the living, became established in English around the late 1300s, returning ‘the word toward its likely prehistoric sense’ tied to ideas of fury, anger or supernatural force as attested in the Old-English verb *gæstan*, ‘to frighten’ (Harper, n.d.). The passage creates a profound irony; the Danes, seeking help against one monster (Grendel), turn to an even more dangerous ‘monster’, the ghost/soul-slayer, who threatens their eternal existence in exchange for their worldly one.

The distinction between *sāwol* (soul) and *gast* (spirit or ghost) is thus both linguistic and theological. *Sāwol* refers specifically to the immortal, accountable essence of a person, the seat of eternal judgment in Christian thought, while *gast* denotes a more general, often supernatural or spectral force. The use of *gastbona* instead of *sāwolbona* is hence deliberate. It underscores the fearful, demonic character of the spiritual threat. In this regard, it is worth noting that Leslie Lockett’s *Anglo-Saxon Psychologies in the Vernacular and Latin Traditions* (2011), which provides perhaps the most comprehensive study of Old English psychological vocabulary, demonstrates that *sāwol* operated within a complex semantic field, including *gæst* (spirit, breath, ghost), *mōd* (mood, mind, heart, courage), *heorte* (heart), *hyge* (thought, mind) and *ferhð* (spirit, life). About the meanings of OE *sāwol* and its relation to *gast*, she explains that

the OE word *sāwol* signifies an entity that joins the body at the beginning of the life-span, leaves the body at death, and participates in the afterlife: this much is true throughout the corpus of OE literature, in narrative as well as in theological discourse. *Sāwol* is more or less interchangeable with *gast* as a name for the human soul, although the word *gast* has an additional range of meanings not shared by *sāwol*: *gast* can refer to God (especially the holy Spirit), angels, saints, demons, the monster Grendel, fire, breath, and the mortal soul of non-human animals. [...]*S**awol* does not share the semantic flexibility of *gast* and cannot be used to signify a variety of elusive or invisible entities (Lockett, 2011, pp. 19–38).

3. Old English *Sāwol*: Excerpt from *The Vespasian Psalter* (c. Eighth Century)

Having explored *sāwol*'s nuanced role in *Beowulf*, straddling the threshold between pagan fatalism and emergent Christian morality, we now turn to its more unambiguous Christian articulation in *The Vespasian Psalter*⁵ (c. 725–750 CE), the earliest surviving example of Old-English biblical translation and glossing (Thomas, 2017; Pulsiano, 1996). *The Vespasian Psalter* represents an elite monastic effort to create an English Christian vocabulary by translating the Latin Vulgate. This is institutional memory-hosting through translation. This text (and similar glossed texts) created the English Christian vocabulary. Most later Christian soul-usage builds on equivalences established here.

85. ORATIO DAVID./

onhaeld dryht eare ðine to me 7 geher mec / for ðon weðla 7 ðearfa ic
 1. INCLINA DNE AUREM TUAM AD ME ET EXAUDI ME, / QUM EGENUS ET PAUPER SUM
 eam / hald sawle mine for ðon halig ic eam / halne doa ðiow ðinne god
 EGO. / 2. CUSTODI ANIMAM MEAM QUM SCS SUM / SALUUM FAC SERUUM TUUM DS
 min / gehyhtendne in ðec / mildsa me dryht for ðon to ðe ic cleopade alne deg /
 MEUS / SPERANTEM IN TE. / 3. MISERERE MIHI DNE QUON AD TE CLAMAUI TOTA DIE /
 geblissa sawle ðeowes ðines / for ðon to ðe dryht ic hof sawle mine /
 (4) LAETIFICA ANIMAM SERUI TUI / QUIA AD TE DNE LEUAUI ANIMAM MEAM. / 4. (5)
 for ðon ðu dryhten wynsum 7 milde earð / [83^r] 7 gentsum in mildheortnisse allū
 QUM TU DNE SUAUIS AC MITIS ES / ET COPIOSUS IN MISERICORDIA OMNIB;
 gegegendum ðec / mid earum onfoh dryht gebed min / 7 behald stefne
 INUOCANTIB: TE. / 5. (6) AURIBUS PERCIPE DNE ORATIONEM MEAM / ET INTENDE UOCI
 boene minre / in dege geswines mines ic cleopede to ðe / for ðon
 DEPRECATIONIS MEAE. / 6. (7) IN DIE TRIBULATIONIS MEAE¹ CLAMAUI AD TE / QUONIAM
 ðu geherdes me / nis gelic ðe in godū dryht / 7 nis efter werce
 EXAUDISTI ME. / 7. (8) NON EST SIMILIS TIBI IN DIIS DNE / ET NON EST SECUNDUM OPERA
 ðinum / alle ðeode swe hwelce² ðu dydes / cumað 7 weorðiað biforan ðe
 TUA. / 8. (9) OMNES GENTES QUASCUMQ: FECISTI / UENIENT ET ADORABUNT CORAM TE
 dryht / 7 ariað noman ðinne / for ðon micel ðu earð 7 donde
 DNE / ET HONORIFICABUNT NOMEN TUUM. / 9. (10) QUONIAM MAGNUS ES TU ET FACIENS
 wundur / ðu earð god ana / gelaed mec dryht in wege ðinū 7 ic gongu in
 MIRABILIA / TU ES DS SOLUS. / 10. (11) DEDUC ME DNE IN UIA TUA ET AMBULABO IN
 soðfestnisse ðinre / blissie heorte min ðæt hie ondrede noman ðinne /
 UERITATE TUA. / 11. (-) LAETETUR COR MEUM UT TIMEAT NOMEN TUUM / (12)
 ic ondettu ðe dryht god min in allre heortan minre / 7 ariu noman ðinne
 CONFITEBOR TIBI DNE DS MEUS IN TOTO CORDE MEO / ET HONORIFICABO NOMEN TUUM
 in ecnisse / for ðon mildheortnis ðin micelu is ofer mec / 7 ðu³ ge-
 IN AETERNUM. / 12. (13) QUONIAM MISERICORDIA TUA MAGNA EST SUPER ME / ET ERIPU-
 neredes sawle mine of helle ðere niðerran / god ða unrehtwisan areosun
 ISTI ANIMAM MEA EX INFerno INFERIORI. / 13. (14) DS INIUSTI INSURREXERUNT
 in mec / 7 gesomnung mehtigra sohtun sawle mine / 7 non foresettun ðec
 IN ME / ET SYNAGOGA POTENTIUM QUAESIERT ANIMA MEA / ET NON PROPOSUERUNT TE

⁵ *The Vespasian Psalter* is the conventional name for an eighth-century manuscript containing the Latin Psalter (a liturgical collection of the 150 Psalms of David arranged for devotional use) accompanied by Old English gloss (an interlinear word-for-word translation of the Latin text). The gloss is in the Mercian dialect of Old English. Likely produced in southern England, possibly at St Augustine's Abbey in Canterbury, *The Vespasian* offers vital evidence for the development of written Old English, the spread of Christian literacy, and the integration of native vocabulary into theological discourse. It also serves as a key witness to early medieval manuscript production (Kuhn, 1965).

Figure 1. Psalm 85 (*Oratio David*) from the eighth-century *Vespasian Psalter* (Kuhn, 1965, p. 83).

In this bilingual psalter, *sāwol* consistently translates Latin *anima*, as shows Figure 1, where *sawle* corresponds to *animam* (accusative of *anima*). This systematic pairing throughout the manuscript suggests that *sāwol* had achieved stable lexical status within the religious register by the eighth century and that the religious domain was a primary locus for the preservation and development of soul-related vocabulary in Old English. This pattern would profoundly influence the term's semantic evolution throughout the medieval period.

(1) Psalm 85:2

Latin: *Custodi **animam meam**, quoniam sanctus sum.*

Old English gloss: *heald **sawle mine**, for ðon halig ic eam*

Modern English: Guard **my soul**, for I am holy.

Here, *sawle* is the direct object of *heald* ('keep, guard'), mirroring Latin *animam* as the object of *custodi*. The possessive *mine* reflects *meam*.

(2) Psalm 85:4

Latin: *Laetifica **animam** servi tui, quia ad te Domine levavi **animam meam**.*

Old English gloss: *geblissa **sawle** ðeowes ðines, for ðon to ðe Drihten ic hof **sawle mine***

Modern English: Rejoice the **soul** of your servant, for to you, O Lord, I have lifted up **my soul**.

Sawle occurs twice in this verse, glossing *animam* in both clauses. The phrase *sawle ðeowes ðines* conveys Latin *animam servi tui*, while *hof sawle mine* renders *levavi animam meam*.

(3) Psalm 85:12

Latin: *Eripuisti **animam meam** ex inferno inferiori.*

Old English gloss: *þu generedes **sawle mine** of helle þere nioðerran*

Modern English: You have delivered **my soul** from the lowest hell.

The verb *geheredes* (past tense of *nerian*, 'to save/deliver') governs *sawle mine*, which corresponds to *animam meam*.

(4) Psalm 85:13

Latin: *Synagoga potentium quaesierunt **animam meam**.*

Old English gloss: *gesomnung mehtigra sohtun **sawle mine***

Modern English: An assembly of violent men [the mighty] have sought **my life [soul]**.

Sohtun (Mercian dialect form of *sōhton*, 'they sought') matches Latin *quaesierunt*, and *gesomnung* ('assembly') renders Latin *synagoga*. The English translation of the Septuagint version of the Old Testament by Sir Lancelot Charles Lee Brenton (1851) – on which the modern English

translation of the excerpts above is based – translated the word *sawle* in this verse as ‘life’ while the King James Bible rendered it as ‘soul’.

These examples offer a compelling glimpse into the semantic consolidation of the Christian concept of the ‘soul’ within early Anglo-Saxon religious discourse. Semantically, *sawle* in this excerpt operates within a clearly Christianised register. Its referent is a theologically loaded entity capable of being preserved, gladdened, uplifted and delivered from hell. This is a profound development in the semantic career of the word, marking its transition from potential Germanic heritage to a fully acculturated term of Christian anthropology and eschatology.

It is interesting to note in this context that from the PIE root *anā-* (to breathe) came the Latin words *animus* (reason, mind, spirit) and *anima* (soul, spirit, life, breath), the Greek *anemos* (wind) and Middle Welsh *eneit* (soul, from which comes the name Enid). It is also noteworthy that the Greek word for soul (*psūkhē*) comes from *psūkhein*, to breathe (Watkins, 2000). The Latin word *anima*, for which *sāwol* was used as a translation equivalent in religious texts ‘exerted considerable influence on the semantic development of the English word’ (OED, n.d.).

Lockett (2011) notes that early Christian thinkers were divided on what constituted a human. Some argued for a tripartite model: a physical body (flesh), an animating soul (*anima* in Latin, *psūkhē* in Greek), and an intellectual faculty (*spiritus* in Latin, *pneuma* in Greek). Others, however, insisted on a bipartite model, including the body (flesh) and a unitary soul (*anima*), a single entity combining all non-physical functions: bodily animation, mental activity, rationality and the capacity for afterlife survival. In Anglo-Saxon England, this scholarly debate was reflected in two distinct traditions: the learned, Christian tradition (what Malcolm Godden (1985) calls the ‘classical tradition’ and Soon Ai Low (1998) labels as ‘expert psychology’) and the vernacular tradition (using Godden’s label), which Low describes as ‘common-sense psychology’.

The classical tradition, which was Latin-influenced, adopted the bipartite model with a unitary soul, where *sāwol* was used to translate *anima* in Christian Latin theology. However, most OE literature – especially poetry, which was less constrained by Latin sources – reveals a different system with a fourfold model consisting of the body, *sāwol* (the part that journeys to the next world after death), *feorh* (also called *ealdoro* or *lif*, the life-force that animates the body) and *mod* (also called *hyge*, *sefa* and *ferhð*, the mind, seat of psychological/mental functions, where *mod* (mood in modern English) could also mean ‘courage’ or ‘pride’ (Kiricsi, 2010)). These four entities – the body, life-force, mind and afterlife soul – form the foundational psychology for most narrative and lyric poetry in Old English.

4. Late Middle/Early Modern English Soule

As we move forward in time, we notice that the Middle-English soul discourse occurs within a dramatically different religious culture. While the church in Britain was increasingly centralised under Rome, influenced by reformed monasticism, scholastic university theology and pastoral care initiatives mandating lay religious instruction, the Norman Conquest of 1066 orchestrated perhaps the most dramatic transformation in the English language history. Overnight, England became a

trilingual society: Latin for the Church, French for nobility and administration, and English retreated to the kitchens, fields and common folk. As historian Turville-Petre elegantly described it, this was 'one culture in three voices', each interpenetrating and influencing the others (Lerer, 2007, p. 54).

This linguistic upheaval triggered changes more profound than any before or since. The English vocabulary underwent a radical transformation as many Old English words now existed side by side with new synonyms (Sylvester et al., 2022), while others disappeared, being displaced (and in some cases ultimately replaced) by an influx of French and Latin terms (Baugh & Cable, 2005). New words shaped the Middle-English religious discourse, including the words 'religion', 'saint', 'prayer', 'sermon', 'confession', 'penance', 'communion', 'sacrament', 'trinity', 'virgin', 'miracle', 'clergy', 'divine', 'immortal', 'eternal', 'virtue', 'charity', 'mercy', 'grace', 'devotion', 'passion' (in the sense of Christ's suffering), 'salvation', 'damnation', 'resurrection' ('the rising again of Christ after his death and burial'), 'preach', 'baptise', 'crucify'. All these words entered English between the twelfth and the fourteenth centuries (Harper n.d.), permanently altering the language's spiritual vocabulary. 'Sound shifts and grammatical restructuring no doubt say a great deal about the typology of a language because they are of a systematic nature. Vocabulary, in contrast, is more likely to reveal something about the world the speakers lived in' (Gramley & Gramley 2005, p. 12). England's world was changing dramatically.

Around 1250, significant political and social changes were occurring that further affected the language situation. England lost Normandy to France (1204), and the nobility gradually gave up their estates abroad. This separation from France contributed to a decline in the need and desirability of using French. By the time of the Barons' Revolt (1258–1265),⁶ the trend among the nobility was shifting towards English monolingualism.

'The Barons of England' lost their lands across the Channel. Henceforth they would be born, brought up and based exclusively in England. So would the king. Families might still retain memories of their Norman ancestry, but the logic of embracing an entirely English identity was now overwhelming. Fittingly King John (1199–1216) was the first king to drop altogether the 'French and English' form of address in his documents. His subjects were now all English (Carpenter, 2004, p. 8).

As the upper classes embraced English, they brought their French vocabulary with them, creating a second much larger lexical avalanche. Between 1250–1400, a large number of all French words that would ever enter English arrived. Borrowings typically reflected the form of French spoken in England (Anglo-Norman⁷) and covered fields like law, fashion, governance and art. Some

⁶The Barons' Revolt (1258–1265) was a conflict between King Henry III and a coalition of rebellious/reformist barons. Sparked by discontent over Henry's fiscal mismanagement and favouritism towards foreign courtiers, the revolt aimed to enforce constitutional reforms to curb royal power and authority and expand parliamentary power (Ridgeway, 2014). Though suppressed, the revolt influenced later constitutional developments, including the evolution of parliamentary representation (Knowles, 1982). This political unrest helped weaken ties with France and encouraged the Anglo-Norman nobility to see themselves more as English.

⁷*Anglo-Norman* was the variety of Old French spoken by the Norman ruling class in England after the Norman Conquest (1066). It developed distinct features due to contact with English and eventually diverged from continental French.

of the later scholars lamented this lexical deluge. Alexander Gil⁸ (1564–1635) remarked in his *Logonomia Anglica* (1619):

About the year 1400, Geoffrey Chaucer, star of ill-omen, rendered his poetry notorious by the use of Latin and French words. Such is the stupidity of the uneducated masses [...]. Thus today we are, for the most part, Englishmen not speaking English and not understood by English ears. [...] O cruel country! (Lerer, 2007, p. 148)

By the fifteenth century, however, English ultimately displaced both Latin and French, completing its restoration as England's primary written and spoken language (Baugh & Cable, 2005). One of the key forces driving this 'vernacular resurgence' (Lerer, 2007) was the Lollard movement in the late fourteenth century. The Lollards were followers of John Wycliffe (c. 1320–1384), an Oxford theologian who challenged papal authority and called for church reform. The name 'Lollard' likely derives from the Dutch word *lollaert* (mumbler or mutterer), adopted in late Middle English as a derogatory term for religious dissidents or heretics (Harper, n.d.).

Wycliffe argued that the Bible, not the church tradition, should be Christianity's ultimate authority, and he initiated the first complete translation of the Bible into English (completed by his followers around 1384). Labelled heretical, the Lollards were burnt under Henry IV's *de Heretico Comburendo* statute (1401) and their movement was largely suppressed (New Catholic Encyclopedia, n.d.). Nevertheless, their work persisted underground and significantly influenced later Protestant reformers (Hudson, 1988). The struggle to replace Latin with English in the domain of religion was, in this sense, a struggle for power (Gramley & Gramley, 2005).

The advent of printing in 1476 by William Caxton, a Kentish-born merchant, marked a turning point in the history of English standardisation and the dissemination of London English. Establishing his press in Westminster, Caxton became England's first printer and quickly recognised the problem of dialectal variation. He famously noted, '*our langage now vsed varyeth ferre from that whiche was vsed and spoken what I was borne*' and '*comyn englysshe that is spoken in one shyre varyeth from a nother*' (Lerer, 2007, p. 99). The fifteenth and sixteenth centuries also saw a rise in literacy and personal letter writing. Families like the Pastons used spelling conventions to represent pronunciation and orthography changes, especially as inflections were increasingly lost, contributing to a move towards a more fixed word order and many spelling changes.

In parallel with the political, religious and social changes, English underwent major orthographic and phonological changes, while literacy expanded beyond monastic circles into lay, mercantile and aristocratic households. By the fifteenth century, the Old English *sāwol*, which survived the seismic English vocabulary changes, had transformed into various Middle English spellings, including *soule*, which became increasingly standardised in written texts.

⁸ English scholar, educator and spelling reformer best known as the high-master of St Paul's School in London, where he taught John Milton. He authored *Logonomia Anglica* (1619), an English grammar (written in Latin) advocating phonetic spelling reforms. His career reflects the intersection of Renaissance pedagogy and early efforts to systematise English spelling and grammar.

Nouns ending in *-e* were a notable feature of Middle and Early Modern English, reflecting broader morphological and phonological changes in the language. In Middle English, the phonological process of vowel reduction resulted in the levelling of all ‘unaccented post-tonic vowels’ (a, e, o and u) to a single neutralised sound, commonly represented orthographically as final *-e*. In simpler terms, when a word had an unstressed vowel after its main syllable, that vowel was simplified to a generic ‘uh’ sound (like the *e* in ‘the’) and spelled with *-e*, no matter what the original ending vowel was (Moore, 1928). For example, in Old English *nama*, the second vowel (post-tonic) was unstressed. So *nama* became *name* /'na:mə/ (later /neim/ in Modern English). This contributed to the simplification of Old English’s complex inflectional system and the widespread appearance of final *-e* in Middle English (Moore, 1928). In other cases, the terminal *-e* was used to indicate that the preceding vowel should be pronounced with a longer sound, marking what linguists call a ‘long vowel’ (e.g. ‘made’ vs ‘mad’).

Additionally, final *-e* developed a specialised grammatical function as a marker of feminine singular nouns (Moore, 1928). Moore observes that research suggests the feminine *-e* occurred after the general vowel levelling process, which turned the a/o/u ending into a uniform *-e*. In Old English, nouns were classified as masculine, feminine or neuter, with distinct inflectional endings for each gender. The noun *sāwol* was **grammatically feminine** as noted in Bosworth and Toller’s *Anglo-Saxon Dictionary* (2014). By Middle English, inflection was greatly reduced, and gender distinctions became less clear in noun forms (Skrytska, 2019). By the seventeenth–eighteenth centuries, the *-e* in noun endings began to disappear from common speech, though it lingered in Poetic/archaic language (e.g. *olde* for stylistic effect). This is how *soule* turned into the modern **soul**.

5. Late Middle English *Soule*: Excerpt from *The Paston Letters* (1465)

*The Paston*⁹ *Letters* (1422–1509), a corpus of family correspondence, provide a valuable vernacular example from East Anglia (Norfolk dialect), showing how *soule* functioned in everyday correspondence. The letters provide rare access to non-literary, non-clerical, everyday language of literate laity. They capture mid-fifteenth century usage during the Wars of the Roses and the pre-Reformation. Comparing the Paston soul-usage (‘secular’, pragmatic, formulaic) with *Beowulf* (heroic-poetic) and *The Vespasian Psalter* (liturgical) shows the soul as a social category with practical consequences. In a letter dated October 29, 1465, Agnes Paston (d. 1479), the matriarch of the Paston family, writes to her son John (1421–1466), deploying *soule* within a discourse blending pragmatic concerns with moral counsel.

*Sonne, [...]*¹⁰

⁹ The Pastons belonged to the gentry class, a rising landowning family in fifteenth-century Norfolk, England, situated between the nobility and the peasantry. They were wealthy, educated and socially ambitious, but not of noble birth. They were part of the emerging literate elite, using education, marriage and legal expertise to consolidate wealth and influence. Much of their surviving correspondence revolves around land disputes, inheritance, family alliances and social advancement (Richmond, 2022; Castor, 2023).

¹⁰ Archaic spellings reflect Middle English conventions. ȝ (yogh): similar to Modern English ‘y’; *ȝoure* = your, *ȝe* = ye (you), *ȝow* = you. þ (thorn): represents ‘th’ (either voiced as in ‘this’ or voiceless as in ‘thin’); *þe* = the, *þer-fro* = therefrom,

*Be my counseyle, dyspose 3oure-selfe as myche as 3e may to haue lesse
to do in þe worlde. 3oure fadyr sayde, 'In lityl bysynes lyeth myche reste.'
þis worlde is but a þorough-fare of woo, and whan we departe þer-fro,
ri3th nou3ght bere with vs but oure good dedys and ylle. And þer knoweth no man how soon God woll clepe
hym, and þer-for it is good for euery creature to be redy. Quom God vysyteth, him he louyth.*

*And as for 3oure breþeren, þei wyll I knowe certeynly laboren all þat in
hem lyeth for 3ow.*

Oure Lorde haue 3ow in his blyssed kepyng, body and soule.

Writen at Norwyche þe xxix day of Octobyr.

By 3oure modir A. P. (Lerer, 2007, 107)

As far as the language is concerned, compared to the Old English texts we examined earlier, it is generally much easier – with some knowledge of the spelling norms – for a modern reader to understand this Late ME text without translation. As for the context of the excerpt, Agnes Paston's use of *soule* reflects the domestication of Christian spirituality into everyday family correspondence. Her use of *soule* situates the word within the framework of Christian piety, but the tone is neither doctrinal nor liturgical; it is affective and practical. The passage blends religious counsel with worldly wisdom. The moral counsel about worldly detachment (*þis worlde is but a þorough-fare of woo*) and spiritual preparation (*it is good for euery creature to be redy*) shows the soul concept functioning within domestic religious instruction: a mother advising her son about the care of his spiritual welfare with the same practical concern she might show for his physical health or financial affairs. This reflects a significant democratisation of the soul-discourse from the specialised vocabulary of monastic or courtly literature to the religious language of the literate merchant class.

She employs *soule* in a formulaic blessing (*body and soule*) that demonstrates how the soul was integrated into conventional expressions.

6. Possessive Soules: Excerpt from Edmund Spenser's *The Faerie Queene* (1596)

'Spenser's impact on English literature was immediate, wide-ranging, and durable also because he chose the medium of print to publish his works rather than having them circulate only in manuscript copies' (Berensmeyer, 2019, p. 370). Like *Beowulf*, *The Faerie Queene* draws on epic conventions, incorporating heroic protagonists, grand quests, battles with monsters and a world where the fate of individuals reflects larger cosmic or moral struggles. But while *Beowulf* is mythical, the *Faerie Queene* is allegorical, directly inspiring later works by John Bunyan (Golder, 1930), Shakespeare, Milton (Vaught, 2025), C. S. Lewis (Rovang, 2014) and the fantastic genre in general. 'Spenser took his place alongside Shakespeare and Milton in the pantheon of British poets, native geniuses "as great...as ever were produced in Rome or Athens"' (O'Callaghan, 2010).

The Faerie Queene was published in the late Elizabethan period, after the Reformation but during ongoing Protestant-Catholic tensions. It synthesises the medieval allegorical tradition with

þorough-fare = thoroughfare, *clepe* = archaic verb meaning 'to call', *quom*: archaic term for 'whom', *myche* = much, *woll* = will, *vysyteth*, *louyth*: older verb endings (-*eth*) equivalent to modern -s (e.g. visits, loves).

Protestant moral theology. The poem is an explicitly Protestant epic dedicated to Elizabeth I. It is a fusion of classical Epic (e.g. Virgil's *Aeneid*, Homer's *Odyssey*), chivalric Romance (knights, dragons, castles, fair maidens), Renaissance Neoplatonism (the idea that physical beauty reflects divine truth), religious allegory (Protestant theology vs Catholicism), and political propaganda (glorifying Elizabeth I). It is structured as a series of six Books, following the adventures of six knights, each of whom represents a virtue (Holiness, Temperance, Chastity, Friendship, Justice, Courtesy); together they form a Renaissance utopia of educating the ideal person. The knights strive to serve the Faerie Queene, Gloriana, who symbolises Queen Elizabeth I. In a broad sense, psychomachia – literally, 'battle of the soul', the war fought within the soul between its virtues and its vices – frameworks the whole poem as all the battles in Faeryland dramatise a continuous spiritual battle.

Spenser's overarching view of the soul in the poem as a whole can be read through a Renaissance Aristotelian-Galenic lens in that the poem treats the body and the soul as a deeply interconnected whole (Broaddus, 2004). In Book II (Temperance), Spenser uses a castle (the House of Alma) as an allegory for the entire human person; its mistress, Alma, explicitly represents the soul. The castle's lower rooms represent bodily functions like digestion and appetite, while its upper chambers represent the faculties of imagination (Phantastes, sage of the future), judgment (an unnamed counsellor, sage of the present) and memory (Eumnestes, sage of the past) (Méndez, 2020). Just as Alma governs every room of her castle, the soul governs the body. This mirrors the Aristotelian-Galenic understanding of the body as the *form*, the animating principle of the body, inseparable from it. The poem also suggests that physical frailty and moral weakness are intertwined, and that no human virtue alone (e.g. the knight of temperance, Guyon) can overcome mortality – the curse of physical decay inherent in living flesh (embodied in the figure of Maleger) – which requires the intervention of Magnificence, the perfection of all virtues (represented by Prince Arthur).

Some critics note that this model resists both medieval ascetic dualism ('body as prison') and later Cartesian separation. 'We should avoid imputing to *The Faerie Queene* sharp oppositions between nature, physicality, and the body on the one hand, and grace, spirit, and soul on the other; or between Books I and II, or Holiness and Temperance' (Borris, 2001).

In Early Modern English, the term *soules* served both as a possessive singular form (equivalent to modern soul's) and a plural noun (equivalent to souls). This morphological form shows how the apostrophe to mark possession had not yet become standardised in Early Modern English, which means that context alone determined the grammatical function of the word. The following excerpt from *The Faerie Queene* illustrates this possessive usage.

*Shee sight from bottome of her wounded brest,
 And after, many bitter throbs did throw
 With lips full pale and foltring tongue opprest,
 These words she breathed forth from riuen chest;
 Leaue, ah leaue off, what euer wight thou bee,
 To let a wearie wretch from her dew rest,*

And trouble dying soules tranquilitiee.

(Spenser, 1596/1995, Book 2, Canto I, St. XLVIII, ll. 1–8)

In this passage, a dying woman pleads to be left alone in her final moments. She begs the onlooker to stop disturbing her and allow her to pass peacefully, ... Her lips are pale, and her trembling, weak tongue struggles to speak. The phrase *dying soules tranquilitiee* refers to the peace she seeks in death, which she feels is being interrupted by the observer's presence.

With Spenser's use of *soules*, we notice a shift in the soul discourse from doctrinal or domestic religious instruction to an increasingly affective register. Unlike the functional or theological usages in the *Vespasian Psalter* or the Paston Letters, Spenser's soul is dramatized; it feels, it suffers, and it longs for peace. This artistic rendering of the soul anticipates the emotional and psychological interiority that becomes more prominent in seventeenth- and eighteenth-century religious and literary texts.

7. Plural *Soules*: Excerpt from *King James Bible* (1611)

Following the affective and poetic invocation of *soules* in *The Faerie Queene*, we now turn to a very different register in the period's most influential text: the *King James Bible* (KJV). Authorised by King James I, the KJV was produced by 47 scholars and became the standard Protestant Bible in the English-speaking world for long centuries. It thus represents state-sponsored, officially authorised memory-hosting, reflecting a deliberate effort by the Church of England to establish normative Protestant vocabulary. Unlike individual authors or limited manuscripts, KJV achieved mass circulation (printed, church lecterns, household Bibles). It demonstrates translation as a memory-hosting act with massive cultural consequences. KJV translators' choices encoded specific Protestant theology that became 'natural' English.

The following excerpt from Genesis 46:15 mentions *soules*, in the plural, with almost a demographic meaning that reflects the Hebrew source word.

These bee the sonnes of Leah, which she bare vnto Iacob in Padan-Aram, with his daughter Dinah: all the soules of his sonnes and his daughters, were thirtie and three (Genesis 46:15, KJV, 1611).

In this passage, *soules* translates the Hebrew term *nephesh* (נֶפֶשׁ). In biblical Hebrew, *nephesh* broadly denotes a 'living being' or 'person' (*nephesh hayyah*, 'living soul'). The KJV's use of *soules* here reflects this original sense, referring collectively to Jacob's children as individual persons. Lucas John Mix (2018) notes that the notorious Greek translation of the Bible, the Septuagint, from the third-century BCE, which 'shaped later opinion through its vocabulary' (Mix, 2018, p. 81), translated *nephesh* as *psūkhē*. Unlike the Greek *psūkhē*, *nephesh* does not imply an immortal, immaterial soul, for '[a]nimals, including humans, do not possess a soul (*nephesh chay*); they are a soul, and that only while the breath moves the dust. Hebrew authors used an entirely different word, 'shade' (*rephaim*) to refer to the remnant that persists after death' (Mix, 2018, p. 83). This translation led to what one might call a conceptual 'blurring', as the Hebrew concept is fundamentally about embodied life, not a soul opposed to the body. The same thing happened with the Latin Vulgate translation which translated *nephesh* as *anima*.

An unbiased analysis of the biblical text itself, especially the Old Testament, will reveal that ‘soul’ and ‘spirit’ (Hebrew: *nephesh* and *ruach*; Greek: *psyche* and *pneuma*) have quite different meanings than they do in Platonic circles. They are used of animals and humans alike and have more to do with the power of life and breath in the earthly creature than anything remotely connected with immortal existence after death (Cooper 1989, p. 3).

This flattening of *nephesh* into *anima*/*psūkhē* was transmitted into English through successive translations. For instance, the *Wycliffe Bible* (c. 1382), the first complete English Bible, was not translated from the original Hebrew and Greek but from the Latin Vulgate (Solopova, 2016). Because Wycliffe and his associates had no access to the Hebrew *nephesh*, they inherited the equation *nephesh* > *anima* > *soule* directly from Jerome’s text. Another example is the *Geneva Bible* (1560), which represented a significant advance in the English translation practice. Produced by English Protestant exiles in Geneva, it was the first English Bible to be based directly on the Hebrew and Greek originals (Berry, 2007). The Geneva translators had access to the Hebrew *nephesh* and could – in principle – use another term, yet they also retained *soule*. The English ‘soul’, inheriting this equivalence, carried it forwards. It can hence be argued that what is ‘remembered’ in it in this context is not exactly the Hebrew *nephesh* but the Septuagint’s and Vulgate’s interpretation of it.

Nevertheless, a deeper reading brings to memory interesting theological developments within the Israelite religion about *nephesh*. Mix (2018, pp. 84–85) explains that between ‘the consolidation of the Tanakh¹¹ as a single volume and before the writing of the Christian scriptures (first- and second-centuries CE)’, doctrines of the afterlife evolved considerably within Second Temple Judaism, producing at least three competing positions: soul annihilation (life ends with the body; associated with the Sadducees), soul reincarnation (the soul returns after death to a new body; associated with the Pharisees), and body–soul dualism (soul leaves the body and persists; associated with the Essenes).

The English word ‘soul’, in rendering *nephesh*, thus carries two memories: the memory of a possible semantic flattening, and the memory of centuries of Jewish debate about what survives death. The KJV, by perpetuating the equivalence *nephesh* > *soule*, transmitted both, without resolving their tension.

A critical distinction must be drawn here between simple linguistic polysemy and cultural memory. Polysemy describes the synchronic coexistence of multiple meanings for a single sign (e.g. soul as ‘metaphysical essence’ vs souls as ‘countable persons’). However, cultural memory explains the diachronic mechanism by which these competing meanings survive. For instance, while the ‘countable person’ meaning of ‘soul’ might have been a natural linguistic drift, it is also a deliberate institutional preservation by the King James Bible translators. While the dominant Scholastic theological discourse had largely solidified ‘soul’ as an immaterial, metaphysical entity, the KJV translation acted as a ‘memory-host’ to retain the older, holistic Hebrew semantic layer. Therefore,

¹¹ The Tanakh is the Hebrew Bible (The Old Testament), the canonical collection of Jewish scriptures. The term is an acronym formed from its three divisions: Torah (Law), Nevi’im (Prophets), and Ketuvim (Writings).

the ‘memory’ is not simply the existence of different meanings, but the active, institutional curation that allows a marginalised semantic layer to persist alongside the dominant one(s), creating a stratified semantic field where the past actively contests the present. Another key distinction is that while polysemy is usually coded in dictionaries, cultural memory often persists in shadows of meanings, subtle connotations that can only be inferred.

8. Plural Soules: Excerpt from John Donne’s *Holy Sonnets* (c. 1609–1617)

Moving from the biblical enumeration of souls as persons, we encounter a dramatically different employment of *soule* in John Donne’s *Holy Sonnet 5*. Here, the concept returns to its most intensely personal and theological dimensions. Donne synthesises a Reformation ‘soul’ (personal faith, direct divine relationship) with Counter-Reformation intensity (emotional devotion, contemplation of death) and metaphysical wit (paradox, argumentation). His work represents the literary memory-host at its most philosophical and emotional sophistication. This is early modern subjectivity. Comparing Donne’s ‘soul’ (existential subject, consciousness) with Spenser’s (allegorical structure) and *The Vespasian Psalter’s* (liturgical object) shows a radical transformation over 900 years that laid the foundation for the modern psychological soul. Donne is a bridge to the Romantic soul (Wordsworth, Keats) and therapeutic soul (twentieth-century self-help culture).

John Donne (1572–1631), the pioneer of seventeenth-century metaphysical poetry, composed his *Holy Sonnets* (c. 1609–1617) during a deeply troubled period in English history, marked by intense spiritual struggle during the sociopolitical volatility of post-Reformation England. Born into a recusant Catholic family at a time when it was a ‘felony’ to practise the Catholic religion, Donne witnessed first-hand the precariousness of faith in Elizabethan society. The regime’s persecution was legally and violently coercive. While some could navigate the era through caution or connections, most Catholics ‘could not, if [they] remained faithful to [their] religion, hope to play any part in public life’, and those who refused conformity faced financial ruin, social blackmail, physical torture or worse. New prisons were built specifically for Catholic ‘recusants’. Conditions were horrific (Carey, 1981).

Prisoners were deprived of sleep, until they lost the use of their reason; they were disjointed on the rack; they were rolled up into balls by machinery ‘and soe Crushed, that the blood sprouted out at divers parts of their bodies’ [...] (Carey, 1981, p. 17).

Catholic households were commonly raided, and in the search for priests’ hiding places, walls were knocked down, rooms ransacked and floors torn up. The householder had not only to defray the cost of this damage, but also to pay the searchers for their trouble [...] (Carey, 1981, p. 16).

The financial incentives to join the Church of England were strong. By a statute of 1585, Catholics who refused to attend Anglican services were liable to a fine of £20 a month. An average parish schoolmaster’s salary at the time [...] was £20 a year. Offenders who found themselves unable to pay were to have all their goods and two-thirds of their land confiscated (Carey, 1981, p. 15).

Donne’s own family bore the brunt of these oppressive conditions under the Elizabethan rule. As recusant Catholics, they lived under constant threat of surveillance, financial penalty and violence. His uncle, the Jesuit priest Jasper Heywood, was imprisoned and eventually exiled, while his brother Henry Donne died of plague in jail after being arrested for harbouring a Catholic priest.

Donne converted to Anglicanism in around 1597 and ended up taking Anglican orders in 1615, becoming a preacher (Carey, 1981). However, the persecution reverberates throughout his *Holy Sonnets*, in which the soul's fate is entangled with fear, guilt and the hope of divine mercy. His *Holy Sonnet 5* (Donne, 2005, p. 13) presents a particularly valuable example of *soule* in early seventeenth-century (metaphysical) religious poetry:

*Oh my black Soule, now thou art summoned
By Sickness, Deaths Harold and Champion;
Thou'art like a Pilgrim, which abroad had don
Treason, and darst not turne to whence he's fled,
[...]
Yet grace, if thou repent thou canst not lacke.
But who shall giue thee that grace to begin?
Oh make thy selfe with holy mourning blacke,
And red with blushinge as thou art with Sin.
Or washe thee in Christs blood, which hath this might
That beeing red, it dyes red Soules to whight.*

The opening apostrophe *Oh my black Soule* establishes the soul (in the singular) as both the addressee and the central concern of the poem. This direct address to the soul reflects the Protestant emphasis on individual spiritual accountability and the believer's responsibility for self-examination. Donne's *Soule* is intensely individualised and psychologically interiorised. The adjective 'black' signals the soul's sinful state of moral corruption, spiritual 'death' and separation from divine grace. The shift to plural *Soules* in the closing line universalises the experience, expanding it to encompass all humanity, suggesting both the universality of redemption and the multiplicity of sinful souls requiring salvation.

Sickness is a champion of death, summoning the soul as if to a courtroom. The soul is imagined as a traitorous pilgrim, *which abroad had don / Treason*, emphasising its estrangement from God and incapacity for self-redemption (*But who shall giue thee that grace to begin?*). This likely reflects the Calvinist emphasis on *sola gratia* (grace alone), which holds that salvation is received solely through God's unmerited favour (grace), not by any human effort or good deeds, as opposed to the Catholic teaching that salvation requires grace and human cooperation through faith/work.

Perhaps most characteristic of Donne's metaphysical style is the paradox of Christ's blood: *beeing red, it dyes red Soules to whight*. This alchemical conceit fuses the physical and spiritual, suggesting a mystical purification that transcends both logic and ritual. The verb *dyes* creates a complex pun: Christ's blood both 'dies' (suffers death) and 'dyes' (changes colour). The soul's transformation in the sonnet is marked by striking penitential imagery. It begins as 'black' with sin, turns 'red' with shame (*blushing*) and the blood of Christ, and is ultimately *dyled* white in purification. This progression dramatizes a spiritual rebirth akin to baptism, yet it bypasses sacramental mediation, in an implicit rejection of Catholic theology in favour of a personal, internalised experience of redemption.

Conclusion

The assembled evidence leads to two main conclusions. On the one hand, 'soul' has accumulated distinct semantic layers. The earliest layer (pagan Germanic *sāwol* as a component of a four-fold psychological model) persists beneath later Christian reinterpretations, which themselves are overlaid by Reformation-era metaphysical anxieties and the canonical biblical formulation that uses the term in a demographic sense. Each layer remains detectable through its associated symbols and institutional contexts.

On the other hand, the word's endurance is tightly bound to the institutions that repeatedly re-anchor it, e.g. monastic scriptoria, gentry households, literary salons, private devotional circles, and the state-controlled church. Whenever 'soul' enters a new institutional arena, it is re-encoded to serve that arena's memory-preserving function (ritual prayer, moral exemplum, political allegory, personal confession). This institutional mediation explains why the term retains relevance despite profound theological and cultural upheavals.

This study identifies three primary memory-hosts, that is, institutions and cultural domains that preserve and transmit specific meanings across time, namely, (1) the church (doctrinal authority), (2) folk tradition (popular belief) and (3) literature (semantic innovation). Each memory-host encodes different semantic layers, and their interactions (cooperative, competitive or oppositional) drive meaning change throughout history. The Church functioned as the primary memory-host for the soul's doctrinal meaning, while folk tradition preserved pre-Christian conceptions. Literature mediated between these domains, creating psychologically complex representations.

Nevertheless, the popular usages that emerge in folk tradition could feed back into literary works and even influence later ecclesiastical language (e.g. pastoral sermons that borrow folk metaphors). In addition, because each host usually preserved the word in different media (manuscripts, printed books, oral chants, legal records), the memory of the soul survived even when one host declined (e.g. monastic scriptoria after the Reformation) as the others continued to circulate the term.

Competing meanings persist – with varying strength – across and beneath the textual surfaces. We can identify different layers of the past that coexist in the concept of the soul, with different layers foregrounded depending on genre, audience, institutional framework and historical pressure.

1. The Religious Layer: The soul as a theological entity, immortal, judged by God, destined for salvation, damnation or purgatory. This layer concerns the soul's fate after death, its relation to divine grace and its purification through penance or prayer.

2. The Anthropological Layer: This layer concerns the soul as the principle of embodied life itself – breath, blood, desire, appetite and the concrete, whole person. Unlike the religious layer (which foregrounds the soul's afterlife and judgment), this layer resists dualism and is concerned with what animates the living body now (vs what happens after death).

3. The Psychological Layer: The soul here is the seat of inner experience, memory, emotion, conscience and self-reflection.

4. The Political Layer: The soul as a category of allegiance and order. In the specific context of Reformation Britain, the soul becomes a site of political contestation. To which church does one's soul owe obedience, Rome or the Crown? Recusancy, oath-taking and martyrdom all turned the soul's fidelity into a public, legally consequential act. In this period, the political soul is inseparable from the religious; confessional allegiance is political allegiance. (The later development of the political soul, in which souls become objects of denominational 'recruiting' in subsequent centuries, falls outside the scope of this article.)

5. The Devotional-Everyday Layer (Lay Piety): The soul in lay piety documents (e.g. the Paston letters) operates at the convergence of the earlier four layers. Here, the religious, anthropological/vital and psychological layers converge within a practical register. The soul is cared for through masses and alms as concretely as the body is cared for through food and clothing. It is at once the beneficiary of post-mortem prayers (religious), the animating breath tied to bodily welfare (vital), and the register of daily anxiety, affection and hope (psychological). This layer reveals that for medieval and early modern laity, the soul was a proximate, embodied and socially embedded concern.

These memories did not travel directly from the seventeenth century into modern English. They arrived through the intervening periods, each of which added its own institutional pressures, reactivating some layers, suppressing others and subtly reshaping the connotative shadows the word carries. The Romantic period, for instance, deepened the psychological interiority that Donne's devotional poetry had begun to consolidate, detaching it progressively from its explicitly theological frame and relocating it within the secular vocabulary of feeling, imagination and authentic selfhood. The Victorian period introduced further tension, as scientific naturalism challenged the soul's metaphysical layer while simultaneously intensifying its use as a marker of moral depth and human dignity in social and literary discourse.

These semantic layers do not survive in modern English primarily as recoverable historical facts but as shadows of meaning or connotations that colour the word's usage without being explicitly named or even consciously recognised by its speakers. The memory-hosts selectively retrieve older semantic layers (e.g. the soul as breath of life) and re-fuse them with new historical experiences (e.g. AI consciousness). Accordingly, the soul can today be simultaneously archaic and indispensable. The cultural memories it carries are latent in its semantic layers. Their perpetuation is dependent on the word's 'circulation and remediation', without which the soul's cultural memory may 'become ephemeral, slipping away and out of memory altogether' (Kennedy & Silverstein, 2023).

When modern speakers use the word soul, they perhaps rarely intend its full theological baggage, yet the word arrives already weighted. It carries an instinctive sense of depth and moral seriousness that no synonym quite replicates. It implies something that can be lost, endangered, corrupted or saved, a connotation deposited by centuries of Christian eschatological usage. It also

retains a vitalistic shadow, a sense of soul as animating warmth, as the difference between a living presence and mere existence – that reaches back through the anthropological layer to the Germanic *sāwol* and its possible ancient association with breath and water as life-forces. This is the memory that makes ‘soulless’ so strong a word with meanings that no strictly theological definition can account for.

These shadows are not polysemy in the conventional sense; they are not discrete alternative meanings that context selects among. They are, rather, simultaneous connotative pressures that give the word its peculiar density – what Koselleck would recognise as the contemporaneity of the non-contemporaneous (*Gleichzeitigkeit des Ungleichzeitigen*) operating at the level of felt meaning (vs definition), and what Assmann would identify as cultural memory persisting in the affective and evaluative charge a word carries long after its institutional origins have been forgotten (vs explicit recollection).

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